

Exploring Secondary School Teachers' Perceptions of AI-Enhanced Gamified Learning's Impact on Student Engagement in Kwara State

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Recently, artificial intelligence (AI)-enhanced gamified learning has become a revolutionary teaching method with benefits such as improved assessment accuracy, personalized feedback, and adaptive teaching strategies. Our research explored secondary school educators' perspectives on AI-enhanced gamified learning in Kwara State, Nigeria. Specifically, it explored teachers' views on its advantages, alignment with existing practices, ease of use, resource availability, and impact on classroom interaction. The study adopted a cross-sectional descriptive survey method, targeting 365 secondary school teachers determined using Cohen et al.'s (2018) sample size formula. Data were gathered through a 25-item researcher-designed questionnaire validated by experts in educational technology. The internal consistency test yielded a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.85 at a 0.05 significance level. Data analysis utilized descriptive statistical methods, such as mean scores and standard deviations with IBM SPSS version 26.0. The findings will provide new perspectives into teachers' readiness as well as openness toward adopting AI-driven gamification, while also identifying infrastructural and pedagogical challenges that may affect its implementation. This research adds to the debate on innovative technology-enhanced learning and pedagogical practices in Nigerian secondary schools.

Keywords:
AI-enhanced learning,
Gamification,
Teacher perceptions,
Secondary education.

Introduction

In the last few years, artificial intelligence-based gamified learning has evolved into a groundbreaking pedagogical approach that offers personalized feedback, adaptive challenges, and immersive game-based motivational strategies that enhance student engagement and learning retention (Kassenkhan et al., 2025). Globally, studies have documented the advantages of combining Artificial Intelligence (AI) with gamification—boosted intrinsic motivation, real-time corrective feedback, differentiated instruction, and improved academic outcomes (Xu et al., 2024; Li et al., 2024; Zia

& Noor, 2024; Gkintoni et al., 2025). In West African settings, pilot intervention such as WhatsApp-based AI tutors in Ghana and AI teaching assistants deployed across multiple countries have demonstrated statistically significant learning gains and scalability potential (Henkel et al., 2024). However, empirical investigations examining secondary school teachers' perceptions of AI-enhanced gamified learning in Nigeria, particularly within Kwara State remain virtually non-existent. Existing Nigerian studies have focused predominantly on generic AI awareness or standalone

gamification effects in subjects such as biology and mathematics (Rije, 2025). Thus, there is a critical gap in understanding how AI-powered gamified tools align with teachers' pedagogical beliefs, classroom dynamics, and instructional capacity in the Kwara State context.

The literature on secondary school teachers' perceptions of AI-enhanced gamified learning (though still emerging globally) shows a consistent pattern of both optimism and caution. A qualitative study across Middle Eastern educational settings revealed that teachers viewed AI-driven gamification positively to boost student involvement, motivation and educational accomplishments. However, they also reported constraints related to implementation logistics, need for training, technical glitches, and alignment with curriculum objectives (Alenezi, 2023). Meanwhile, broader AI-in-education research, including work in Southwest Nigeria, indicates that although secondary school teachers acknowledge AI tutoring's positive impact, a substantial proportion (77 %) remain hesitant or negative because of fear of replacement, low AI understanding, or limited professional preparation (Olaseni, 2024). In Sokoto State, a separate survey of chemistry teachers found low awareness of AI tools but positive perceptions of their potential to enhance engagement and individualized instruction, underscoring the gap between belief in AI's value and readiness to apply it in practice (Aliyu, 2025). Furthermore, descriptive investigations in other Nigerian states also documented extremely low actual integration of AI tools into classroom instruction, often due to infrastructural inadequacies and scarce teacher training corresponding to moderate perceived effectiveness in boosting

engagement and retention (Obidiebube et al 2025). Together, these studies emphasize that while teachers generally perceive AI-enhanced gamified learning as promising, systemic barriers, such as awareness, alignment, infrastructure, training, and trust, remain to be addressed before meaningful adoption can occur.

To address these objectives, a descriptive quantitative research design was utilized for the study employed using structured questionnaires distributed to a cross-section of secondary school instructors across selected schools in Kwara State. Data was analysed by utilizing descriptive statistics using standard deviation and mean scores to ascertain prevailing perceptions and resource conditions. The research instrument will include measures corresponding to five specific research questions: perceived advantages, pedagogical alignment, perceived ease of use, resource availability, and perceived effectiveness for classroom interaction.

Statement of the problem

The incorporation of gamification and Artificial Intelligence (AI) for teaching has shown to be promising globally enhancing the involvement of student and educational accomplishments. However, there is a dearth of research on the perceptions and readiness of teachers in secondary school in Kwara State, Nigeria to adopt AI-enhanced gamified learning approaches. The research aimed to examine the perceptions of secondary school teachers in Kwara State, Nigeria, regarding the advantages, alignment with existing pedagogical practices, ease of use, availability of instructional resources, and impact on classroom interaction of AI-enhanced gamified learning. The results of this study will reveal potential gains and

challenges in implementing AI-enhanced gamified learning in secondary schools in Kwara State, Nigeria, offer methods for its efficient adoption as well as implementation.

Purpose of the Study

1. Examine secondary school teachers perceived advantages of AI-enhanced gamified learning in Kwara state.
2. Investigate the extent to which AI-enhanced gamified learning aligns with secondary school teachers' pedagogical practices in Kwara state.
3. Explore secondary school teachers' perceptions of the ease of use of AI-enhanced gamified learning in Kwara state.
4. Assess instructional resources available for secondary school teachers to use AI-enhanced gamified learning for instruction in Kwara state.
5. Assess secondary school teachers' perception of AI-enhanced gamified learning to improve classroom interaction in Kwara state.

Research Question

1. What are secondary school teachers perceived advantages of AI-enhanced gamified learning in Kwara State?
2. To what extent does AI-enhanced gamified learning align with secondary school teachers' existing pedagogical practices in Kwara State?
3. How do secondary school teachers perceive the ease of use of AI-enhanced gamified learning in Kwara State?
4. What instructional resources are available to secondary school teachers for implementing AI-enhanced gamified learning in Kwara State?
5. How do secondary school teachers perceive the effectiveness of AI-

enhanced gamified learning in improving classroom interaction in Kwara State?

Theoretical background based on Diffusion of Innovations Theory

Rogers' (2003)

Diffusion of Innovations theory Rogers' (2003) clarifies how novel concepts and digital tools are adopted and disperse among a social framework. The theory pinpointed four vital elements: communication channels, innovation, time, and social systems. Innovation is perceived as new by individuals, and its adoption is influenced by the communication channels used to disseminate information (Sherry & Gibson, 2002). The social system, including its structure and norms, also has a profound effect on adoption decisions. The innovation decision process involves five stages: knowledge followed by persuasion, decision making followed by implementation, and then confirmation. In the knowledge stage, individuals learn innovation and seek information. The persuasion stage involves forming attitudes toward innovation, whereas the decision stage includes the choice to adopt or reject it (Rogers, 2003). Implementation encompasses practicing innovation, and confirmation includes looking for support to decide (Rogers, 2003).

The perceived characteristics of innovation substantially predict the adoption (Rogers, 2003). These characteristics comprise of relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, trialability, and observability (Rogers, 2003). The Relative advantage is the most significant indicator of the adoption. Other studies have also supported the importance of these attributes in the adoption of innovation, particularly in educational

settings (Casmir, 2001; Finley, 2003; McKenzie, 1999; Parisot 1997; Spotts, 1999). AI-enhanced gamified learning is an innovative instructional strategy with perceived innovation attributes that affect its adoption in an educational setting.

Advantages of AI-Enhanced Gamified Learning

AI-enhanced gamified learning can be productively applied to teaching and learning by enabling students build knowledge and enhance higher-order cognition (Xu et al., 2024). The utilization of AI-enhanced gamified learning led to improved learning outcome, critical-thinking skills, coding skills, learning drive, and absorption experiences (Lin et al. 2020; Chen et al., 2024; Ng et al., 2024). AI-enhanced gamified learning platforms allow students to ask questions and receive instant response as well as more educational materials, allowing them to get over tasks independently and study at their own speed (Ait et al., 2023). AI-enhanced gamified learning can meet students' specific learning demands (Wu et al., 2023), providing tailored learning experiences that can ease students' anxiety and decrease mental effort. (Stathakarou et al., 2020). Many researchers have indicated that AI-enhanced gamified learning can enhance students' learning achievement and develop their intellectual skills, particularly problem-solving skills and creativity skills (Chen et al., 2024). This approach rapidly tracks the problem-solving process and enhances the comprehension of the educational material, which enables learners build advance critical-thinking abilities. Thus, connecting scaffolding to game obstacles can engage and support students' mastery of key concepts, thereby enhancing their academic achievement and fostering deeper game engagement (Kuo et al., 2023).

AI-Enhanced Gamified Learning Aligns with Secondary School Teachers' Existing Pedagogical Practices

Educators recognize the importance of implementing pedagogies that can effectively interpret the curriculum (Ng et al., 2024). Currently, conventional teaching strategies and approaches have failed to sustain students' interest in learning. In addition, owing to students' variability conventional instructional approaches often fail to deliver tailored guidance, limiting the optimization of learning achievements (Hu, 2023). Thus, teachers and other stakeholders have experimented with different innovative teaching strategies, such as AI-enhanced gamified learning.

Olugbenga, (2021) advocates for the integration of games to add "an element of fun to the learning environment", noting that "Gamification has been a huge trend in teaching and learning in recent times" and that "the use of mathematical games like ludomatic, chess etc. helps to improve critical thinking". This establishes a clear pedagogical alignment for gamified learning within the broader framework of modern, effective teaching strategies that focus on students' needs and engagement. However, this study encourages teachers to adapt to modern trends and implement learner-centred methods to prepare students for 21st-century skills, it does not elaborate on the current status or integration of AI in their pedagogical practices. Thus, pedagogical practices now tend to involve the active participation of students, with teachers serving as facilitators.

The study by Escalante et al. (2023) provides analytical intuitions on how AI-generated feedback can be integrated into teaching without disrupting learning outcomes, a finding that directly informs the

discourse on AI-enhanced gamified learning and its alignment with teachers' pedagogical practices. Using a quasi-experimental design with English-as-a-New-Language (ENL) learners, the first research compared the efficacy of AI-generated versus human tutor result assessment of writing performance over six weeks and observed that there was no substantial difference in learning achievements, suggesting that AI tools can complement existing instructional methods rather than replace them. The second study, which gathered student perceptions, revealed a nearly equal preference for AI and human feedback, highlighting that learners value both technological innovation and traditional support. These findings imply that AI can seamlessly be incorporated into existing teaching frameworks, including gamified learning environments, to reinforce learner-centred practices already embraced by teachers. In the context of secondary education, this suggests that AI-enhanced gamification could provide personalized, adaptive feedback and engagement opportunities that align with teachers' established goals of improving student participation and achievement, while also supporting a blended approach that maintains the teacher's critical role.

Teachers can develop immersive participatory lessons tailored to individual learners' requirement by leveraging game-based learning to boost involvement and adaptive technology to customize education (Chen, 2024; Setyoadi, 2024). The integration of AI-enhanced gamified learning into school program has the ability to enhance standard procedures. Artificial intelligence (AI) systems have the ability to foster learning, offer individualised guidance, and support teachers in monitoring student growth (Akavova, 2023; Pency,

2023). Gamification enhances motivation and involvement by presenting game elements into educational settings (Lyons et al., 2023; Hellin, 2023; McNeill, 2024).

Secondary School Teachers Perceive Ease of Use of AI-enhanced Gamified Learning

Using age-appropriate AI-enhanced gamified learning platforms, teachers can facilitate students' understanding of the subject and provide an enjoyable learning experience that captures their attention and enhances their engagement (Ng et al., 2024). Although recent studies had advanced understanding of AI applications in education, they exhibited methodological and contextual limitations that underscored the necessity of the present investigation. For example, Gu (2024) employed a mixed-methods design combining interviews, surveys, and experimental elements which strengthened internal triangulation and yielded important evidence of improved learners involvement and academic achievements; though, the research was situated in higher education and provided limited empirical attention to teachers' usability perceptions, measurement of Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) constructs (especially perceived ease of use), and the contextual barriers that shape classroom adoption.

Likewise, Okunade (2024) offered a valuable, locally grounded retrospective analysis of AI affordances for science education in Nigerian secondary schools highlighting adaptive learning systems, intelligent tutoring systems, and virtual laboratories but the utilization of secondary information constrained the ability to capture teachers' lived experiences, attitudes, and practical concerns (e.g., infrastructural readiness, professional development needs,

and cost implications) through primary measurement. Collectively, these studies left unaddressed the teacher-centred, context-specific questions that determine whether AI-enhanced gamified tools are perceived as easy to use and therefore adoptable in secondary school settings. In response, the present study employed a descriptive survey design with a TAM-based, psychometrically tested instrument and stratified sampling of secondary school teachers in Kwara State to generate primary empirical evidence on perceived ease of use, thus filling both the methodological gap (lack of teacher-focused, validated measures) and the contextual gap (limited evidence from Nigerian secondary schools) evident in the extant literature.

Instructional Resources Available to Secondary School Teachers for Implementing AI-Enhanced Gamified Learning

Globally, instructional resources for the implementation of AI-enhanced gamified learning are continuously being produced and made available for teaching and learning processes. The Gmind AI platform, which partners with the Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN) is an indigenous platform. Other platforms include Curri Pod and Edu Aide AI. Teachers can utilize the platform to prepare interactive lesson plans and generate tailored quizzes. Other tools include Canva Magic Write, Quizizz, Class Craft and ClassDojo, Grade Scope and Zip Grade, Google Translate and Duolingo, and Assignment AI Detector (Banik & Gullapely, 2025; Wu et al., 2025). Teachers can use these instructional online educational resources to implement AI-enhanced gamified learning. Other resources included mobile devices, interactive boards, and computers. Insufficient accessibility to technologies likes mobile devices, tablets and

computers impedes the effective application of AI-enhanced gamified learning in Nigeria (Aina et al.,2023). Furthermore, the epileptic supply of electricity and inadequate access to internet in several schools pose considerable obstacles, impeding the efficient utilization of AI-enhanced gamified learning and hindering learners' educational advancement (Okunade,2024).

Secondary School Teachers Perceived the Effectiveness of AI-Enhanced Gamified Learning in Improving Classroom Interaction

Looking ahead, the future prospects for AI-enhanced gamified learning in education appears bright, especially within the field of learning in Nigeria. A very significant development anticipated is the enhancement and widespread utilization of personalized educational settings. Costa et al. (2024) study on Gamification and AI through a conceptual and model-driven methodology, proposing mathematical frameworks to illustrate how AI can adapt game mechanics, personalize feedback, and predict user behaviour, teacher-focused studies often use survey-based quantitative designs to capture educators' views and classroom experiences. The findings from such perception studies generally indicate that teachers regard AI-enhanced gamification as effective in motivating students, tailoring instruction, and improving participation, which complements the theoretical models by showing real-world applicability. This convergence explains the prospects of AI-driven gamified systems to transform secondary school teaching and learning practices.

Another important development is expected improvement in data analytics. The integration of AI-enhanced gamified learning provides a sophisticated data analysis tool to

change the procedure of assessing learners' improvement, detecting educational dynamics, and uncovering key findings for continuous improvement (Gu, 2024). The breakthrough of natural language processing (NLP) and AI-enhanced gamified learning is predicted to improve ability in understanding and catering to learners' oral and written communications (Okunade,2024). Thus, leading to an immersive and comprehensive educational experiences (Aina et al., 2023).

Methodology

This is a descriptive cross-sectional survey design employed to investigate secondary school teachers' perceptions of AI-enhanced gamified learning in Kwara State. The population of the study is made up of all secondary school teachers in the Kwara state, with a target population of 365. The sample size was determined using Cohen et al.'s (2018) sample size formula. The research instrument was a researcher-designed questionnaire structured into five sections, reflecting the study's objectives: advantages, pedagogical alignment, ease of use, instructional resources, and classroom interaction. To ensure strong alignment with the research objectives, items were developed directly from the stated objectives and supported by relevant literature. For

instance, items on advantages captured aspects such as motivation, performance, and engagement, while ease of use items reflected navigation, training, and instructional clarity. To ensure the validity and reliability of the instrument, the Content validity was established through the review of experts and specialists in educational technology and measurement. A pilot test was conducted with 30 secondary school teachers outside the main study sample to refine item clarity and structure. Feedback led to minor revisions in wording to ensure contextual appropriateness. Reliability was confirmed through Cronbach's alpha analysis with a *value* of 0.85 at a 0.05 significance level, indicating the instrument was reliable. Data collection was conducted through the administered questionnaires, while analysis was carried out using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation with the aid of IBM SPSS version 26.0. This approach provided clear insights into teachers' perceptions across the five research questions.

Results and Discussions

Research Question 1: What are secondary school teachers perceived advantages of AI-enhanced gamified learning in Kwara State?

Table 1:

secondary school teachers' perceptions of the advantages of AI-enhanced gamified learning

S/N	Statement	Mean	St. Deviation
1	AI-enhanced gamified learning increases students' motivation to learn.	2.9781	1.01341
2	AI-enhanced gamified tools promote deeper understanding of subject content.	2.9781	1.01341
3	Students show improved academic performance with AI-gamified instruction.	2.9781	1.01341

4	AI gamification helps teachers identify individual learning needs.	2.5945	0.88017
5	Gamified learning with AI creates a more engaging classroom environment.	2.9096	1.04305

Figure 1: bar chart representation of Secondary School teachers' Perceptions of the advantages of AI-enhanced gamified learning in Kwara State

Table 1 and figure 1 presents secondary school teachers perceived advantages of AI-enhanced gamified learning in Kwara. The findings showed that teachers generally agreed that AI-gamified learning positively influences teaching and learning, particularly in increasing students' motivation (Mean = 2.98, SD = 1.01), promoting a deeper understanding of subject content (mean = 2.98, SD = 1.01), and improving academic performance (Mean = 2.98, SD = 1.01). Similarly, teachers acknowledged that gamified learning with AI made the classroom environment more engaging (mean = 2.91, SD = 1.04). However, perceptions were slightly lower regarding the role of AI gamification in helping teachers

identify their individual learning needs (mean = 2.59, SD = 0.88).

These results suggest that teachers in Kwara State acknowledge the pedagogical value of AI gamification in stimulating learners' interest and enhancing comprehension. This highlights a paradigm shift from traditional didactic methods toward more interactive learning experiences, emphasizing the importance of motivation as a driver of academic achievement. Nonetheless, the lower perception of AI's role in identifying learning needs points to a gap in personalized instruction, suggesting the need for better-designed AI systems or enhanced teacher training in data-driven pedagogies.

The results of the research reveal that secondary school teachers in Kwara State generally perceive AI-enhanced gamified learning as advantageous for improving students’ motivation, participation, and collaborative learning. This is consistent with the existing literature, which affirms that AI-enhanced gamification promotes deeper engagement, problem solving, and higher-order thinking skills (Xu et al., 2024; Lin et al. 2020; Ng et al., 2024). Teachers’ recognition of their ability to improve

academic performance and create engaging classrooms also supports previous studies that highlighted AI gamification as a learner-centred strategy capable of cultivating innovation, problem-solving, and computational thinking skills (Lin & Ye, 2024; Chen et al., 2024).

Research Question 2: To what extent does AI-enhanced gamified learning align with secondary school teachers’ existing pedagogical practices in Kwara State?

Table 2:

Extent AI-enhanced gamified learning aligns with secondary school teachers’ existing pedagogical practices

S/N	Statement	Mean	St. Deviation
1.	AI-enhanced gamified learning fits well with my current teaching methods.	2.6219	1.33818
2.	The use of AI in gamified learning complements my lesson planning strategies.	2.6219	1.33818
3.	Integrating AI-gamified tools does not disrupt my classroom routines.	2.3699	1.19185
4.	My teaching style aligns with the features of AI-enhanced gamification.	2.4685	1.40338
5.	I find it easy to adapt AI-enhanced gamified learning to the curriculum I teach.	2.1342	0.91150

Figure 2: Bar Chart showing the Extent to which AI-enhanced Gamified Learning aligns with Secondary School Teachers’ existing Pedagogical Practices

Table 2 and figure 2 shows teachers’ perceptions of the extent to which AI-enhanced gamified learning aligns with their existing pedagogical practices in Kwara State. The results indicate a moderate level of alignment overall, with teachers agreeing that AI-gamified learning fits their current teaching methods (Mean = 2.62, SD = 1.34) and complements lesson planning strategies (Mean = 2.62, SD = 1.34). However, lower means were recorded for whether AI-gamified tools do not disrupt classroom routines (Mean = 2.37, SD = 1.19) and whether their teaching style aligns with AI gamification features (Mean = 2.47, SD = 1.40). The lowest perception was recorded on the ease of adapting AI-enhanced gamification to the curriculum (Mean = 2.13, SD = 0.91). The moderate alignment indicates that while teachers recognize the value of AI gamification, systemic barriers such as rigid curriculum structures and teacher-centred approaches limit full integration. This emphasises the necessity for curriculum reforms and focused training

initiative to support the seamless adoption of AI-based gamification in Nigeria’s educational system.

In terms of alignment with existing pedagogical practices, the results revealed only a moderate level of fit, particularly regarding adaptability to curriculum and classroom routines. This finding resonates with the literature, which indicates that conventional teacher-centred approaches frequently struggle to offer customized support, thereby hindering peak learning achievements (Hu, 2023). With pedagogy shifting toward learner-centred practices (Olugbenga, 2021), AI-enhanced gamification offers opportunities to bridge this gap by providing immediate feedback, guiding students like human tutors, and tailoring their learning experiences (Escalante, 2023).

Research Question 3: How do secondary school teachers perceive the ease of use of AI-enhanced gamified learning in Kwara State?

Table 3:

Secondary School Teachers Perceived Ease of Use of AI-Enhanced Gamified Learning

S/N	Statement	Mean	St. Deviation
1.	I find AI-enhanced gamified learning platforms easy to navigate.	2.3370	0.62360
2.	Learning to use AI gamification tools requires minimal training.	2.3370	0.62360
3.	I can effectively use AI-gamified tools without external support.	2.1726	0.55501
4.	The instructions on most AI gamification platforms are clear and simple.	2.1014	0.50614
5.	I feel confident using AI-enhanced gamified applications in my teaching.	2.4082	0.63802

Figure 3: Bar chart on Secondary School Teachers Perceived Ease of Use of AI-Enhanced Gamified Learning

Table 3 and figure 3 presents teachers’ perceptions of the ease of use of AI-enhanced gamified learning in Kwara. The results generally reflect a low-to-moderate ease of use, with the highest rating given to teachers’ confidence in using AI-gamified applications (mean = 2.41, SD = 0.64). Teachers also reported that platforms were relatively easy to navigate (mean = 2.34, SD = 0.62) and that minimal training was required (mean = 2.34, SD = 0.62). However, lower ratings were observed for the ability to use AI-gamified tools without external support (mean = 2.17, SD = 0.56) and clarity of instructions on AI platforms (mean = 2.10, SD = 0.51). The results indicate that teachers limited digital literacy and inadequate training remain barriers to adoption. This aligns with Rogers’ (2003) innovation diffusion theory, where perceived complexity hinders adoption. Without deliberate investment in teacher capacity-building, the full benefits of AI gamification may remain underutilized. The findings therefore underscore the need for

continuous professional development and the design of context-appropriate AI platforms with simplified interfaces.

The study also revealed low-to-moderate perceptions of ease of use, with teachers expressing challenges in navigating AI platforms without support, and citing unclear instructional features. Although some studies have reported that AI-enhanced game-based instruction can be easy to use and effective across diverse student groups (Gu, 2024; Okunade, 2024), the present findings highlight a mismatch between potential and reality in the Nigerian context. This may be linked to insufficient training and limited exposure to age-appropriate AI platforms, indicating that perceived complexity, one of Rogers’ (2003) innovation attributes, remains a barrier to adoption. Ensuring that teachers receive adequate training and ongoing support is crucial for enhancing their confidence and reducing the complexity associated with these technologies.

Research Question 4: What instructional resources are available to secondary school

teachers for implementing AI-enhanced gamified learning in Kwara State?

Table 4:

Available instructional resources to secondary school teachers for implementing AI-enhanced gamified learning

S/N	Statement	Mean	St. Deviation
1.	My school provides sufficient devices for implementing AI-gamified learning.	1.2575	0.43788
2.	Reliable internet access is available for AI-enhanced gamification tools.	1.2575	0.43788
3.	I have access to quality software or apps for gamified learning with AI.	1.5644	0.62401
4.	I receive regular training or workshops on using AI in gamified instruction.	1.2575	0.43788
5.	There is administrative support for using AI-enhanced gamified learning in my school.	1.2575	0.43788

Figure 4: radar chart on Available Instructional Resources to Secondary School Teachers for Implementing AI-enhanced Gamified Learning

Table 4 and Figure 4 shows the availability of instructional resources for implementing AI-enhanced gamified learning in secondary schools in Kwara state. The results revealed a generally very low level of resource availability, as indicated by the consistently low mean scores across most items. Teachers reported inadequate provision of devices (mean = 1.26, SD = 0.44), poor Internet access (mean = 1.26, SD = 0.44), lack of regular training or workshops (mean = 1.26, SD = 0.44), and insufficient administrative support (mean = 1.26, SD = 0.44). A slightly higher rating was observed only for access to quality software or apps (mean = 1.56, SD = 0.62), although it was still below the average. The results demonstrate that infrastructural deficits constitute the most significant barrier to effective adoption of AI gamification in Kwara State. Without tackling the foundational obstacles, such as reliable electricity, internet access, and administrative backing the potential of AI-enhanced gamification will remain

unrealized, widening the digital divide in education.

A major constraint identified was the unavailability of instructional resources, with teachers reporting inadequate access to devices, internet connectivity, administrative support, and professional development. The findings from this study align with the observations of Aina et al. (2023), who noted that insufficient access to technological devices hampers effective AI integration in Nigerian schools, and Okunade (2024), who emphasized the negative impact of irregular electricity and poor Internet access. Although global innovations such as Gmind AI, Curri Pod, and Edu Aide AI, and interactive tools such as Quizizz and ClassDojo are available (Banik & Gullapely, 2025; Wu et al., 2025), local infrastructural deficiencies continue to impede widespread adoption.

Research Question 5: How do secondary school teachers perceive the effectiveness of AI-enhanced gamified learning in improving classroom interaction in Kwara State?

Table 5:

Effectiveness of AI-enhanced gamified learning in improving classroom interaction

S/N	Statement	Mean	St. Deviation
1.	AI-enhanced gamified learning increases student participation in class.	3.1315	1.07633
2.	Gamified AI tools promote collaborative learning among students.	3.1288	1.07794
3.	AI-enhanced gamification facilitates timely feedback during lessons.	2.7425	0.85129
4.	My students are more responsive when AI gamification is used in class.	3.0493	1.04449

5. I have observed better teacher-student interaction using AI-enhanced gamification. 2.8110 0.90777

Figure 5: Line Graph on Effectiveness of AI-enhanced Gamified Learning in Improving Classroom Interaction

Table 5 and Figure 5 presents teachers perceived effectiveness of AI-enhanced gamified learning in improving classroom interaction in Kwara State. The results indicate a generally positive perception, with the highest means recorded for increased student participation (Mean = 3.13, SD = 1.08) and promotion of collaborative learning (Mean = 3.13, SD = 1.08), suggesting that AI-gamification actively engages students and fosters peer-to-peer interaction. Similarly, teachers agreed that students were more responsive during lessons when AI-gamification was applied (Mean = 3.05, SD = 1.04). While perceptions of timely feedback (Mean = 2.74, SD = 0.85) and improved teacher-student interaction (Mean = 2.81, SD = 0.91) were slightly lower, they still show moderate agreement. These

findings reinforce the argument that AI gamification has the potential to transform classroom dynamics from passive to active learning environments. By fostering collaboration and responsiveness, it supports 21st-century learning competencies such as teamwork, communication, and problem-solving. However, the lower perceptions of timely feedback and teacher-student interaction reflect infrastructural and training constraints, emphasizing that technology alone cannot replace the human element of effective pedagogy.

Teachers perceived AI-enhanced gamified learning to be effective in promoting classroom interaction, particularly through increased participation, collaboration, and student responsiveness. This aligns with the broader literature that

highlights the prospects of AI gamification to foster personalised educational settings, improve feedback mechanisms, and enhance immersion (Costa et al., 2024; Gu, 2024; Okunade, 2024). The findings suggest that, when effectively integrated, AI-enhanced gamification can strengthen both peer-to-peer and teacher-student interactions, thereby creating more dynamic and inclusive learning environments. However, the moderate ratings for timely feedback and teacher-student interaction imply that while technology holds promise, its effectiveness is curtailed by contextual limitations such as inadequate infrastructure and limited teacher training.

Implication of the Findings

The results of this research, understood through Rogers' (2003) Diffusion of Innovations Theory, demonstrate that teachers' positive perceptions of AI-enhanced gamified learning reflect the attribute of relative advantage, particularly in enhancing student motivation, engagement, and collaboration. However, moderate alignment with pedagogical practices and low-to-moderate ease of use point to challenges of compatibility and complexity, where curricular rigidity, unclear platform instructions, and reliance on external support hinder adoption. The severe lack of resources, training, and administrative support further constrains trialability and observability, limiting opportunities for experimentation and sustained implementation. These results imply that although AI-enhanced gamification has the potential to transform classroom instruction, its effectiveness will remain curtailed unless structural barriers such as inadequate infrastructure and pedagogical constraints are addressed.

The implications are significant for educational policy, teacher training, and future research. Policymakers must prioritize investment in digital infrastructure, reliable internet, devices, and gamification software while promoting supportive policies and partnerships that contextualize AI tools for local use. Teacher education programs should embed digital pedagogy and gamification modules into pre-service and in-service training, ensuring teachers gain both technical competence and pedagogical strategies for integration. For research, longitudinal and comparative studies are needed to examine adoption patterns, while experimental studies could measure direct effects on learning outcomes. Notably, a surprising outcome was the sharp contrast between teachers' recognition of AI gamification's motivational benefits and their low confidence in its ability to personalize learning, suggesting that while gamification supports group dynamics, its adaptive potential remains underutilized. Overall, bridging infrastructural, curricular, and training gaps is crucial if AI-enhanced gamification is to evolve from a promising innovation into a transformative instructional strategy for secondary schools in Kwara State.

Conclusions and Recommendation

The study concluded that secondary school teachers in Kwara State generally hold positive perceptions of AI-enhanced gamified learning, particularly regarding its potential to motivate students, foster participation, and promote collaborative learning. Teachers recognize its value in enriching classroom engagement and improving academic outcomes; however, challenges remain in relation to alignment with existing pedagogical practices, ease of

use, and, most significantly, the availability of instructional resources. Very low access to devices, internet connectivity, training, and administrative support represent major barriers to implementation. Thus, although AI-enhanced gamification shows promise as a transformative instructional approach, its successful adoption in Kwara State schools will depend on targeted interventions to improve resource provision, strengthen teachers' digital competence, and integrate AI tools more effectively into curriculum and pedagogy.

Informed by these results, key recommendations are proposed. Professional development opportunities should focus on building digital competence, reducing complexity, and equipping teachers with strategies to integrate gamification into their teaching methods, thereby addressing the identified challenges of ease of use and pedagogical alignment. For policymakers, investment in digital infrastructure including reliable internet, sufficient devices, and access to quality gamification platforms should be prioritized to bridge the resource gaps identified in the study, alongside establishing supportive policies that encourage innovation in schools. Curriculum developers and administrators should ensure that AI-enhanced gamification is embedded within instructional frameworks to reduce disruptions and improve compatibility with teaching practices. Finally, for future researchers, longitudinal and comparative researches are required to assess the prolonged impacts of AI gamification on academic outcomes, while experimental research could provide evidence on its effectiveness in addressing personalized learning needs. Taken together, these recommendations provide a pathway for translating teachers'

positive perceptions into sustainable adoption and transformative practice.

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